

Reasons that necessitated the Federal University libraries in Nigeria to engage in Resources Sharing Activities

Ibrahim Idi Ahmad

Polytechnic Librarian

Senator Ahmed Babba Kaita Library, Federal Polytechnic, Daura, Katsina State.

ibrahimiatodarya@gmail.com

Sirajo Abubakar Danzangi

University Library Complex Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

sabubakar1@fudutsinma.edu.ng

Bayero Sidi Dangoro

University Library, University of Education, Kano State

Bayerosidi33@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigates the reasons why federal university libraries in Nigeria engage in resource sharing activities. Resource sharing is essential for meeting the diverse needs of library users, particularly in academic settings, and is influenced by various factors, including staff qualifications and experience.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey design was employed for the study, conducted across 40 federal universities in Nigeria. The universities were divided into six geopolitical zones, and a stratified sampling technique was used to select 50% from each zone, resulting in a sample of 20 universities. The target population comprised 580 library staff, to whom questionnaires were administered. Of the 580 distributed, 433 usable responses were returned. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentage, mean score, and standard deviation) through Microsoft Excel and SPSS software.

Findings/Result: The findings revealed that most academic librarians possess the necessary academic qualifications and that resource sharing is a significant activity in these libraries. Key reasons for engaging in resource sharing include promoting the free flow of resources, fostering mutual understanding, and facilitating the exchange of ideas, techniques, resources, services, and experiences among libraries.

Conclusion: Resource sharing plays a crucial role in meeting the needs of library users. The qualifications and experience of library staff are integral to the effective implementation of resource sharing activities.

Recommendations: It is recommended that academic librarians undergo continuous training and retraining to enhance their resource sharing capabilities. Additionally, libraries should implement reward systems and provide adequate budgetary support to foster sustainable resource sharing partnerships.

Key Words: Academic Libraries, Federal University Libraries, Resource Sharing Activities

Introduction

Libraries in universities are the lifeline of learning, teaching, research, and other academic activities in higher institutions. The mission of academic libraries includes providing resources and services that supplement and complement the academic pursuits of the university community. These libraries enhance students' chances of excelling in their studies and keep academic staff and researchers updated with relevant resources in their areas of specialization.

Academic libraries serve as hubs that sustain the academic activities of the entire university community by ensuring access to essential resources and services (Bourlakis & Bourlakis, 2013). Similarly, Obasola (2015) described academic libraries in universities and related institutions as "centers of knowledge, development, and services that support users in their teaching, research, and learning processes, which are fundamental to an academic environment."

Resource sharing among libraries is a valuable practice that enriches collections for the benefit of the patron community. Ali and Owoeye (2010), in their research, *Resource Sharing among Law Libraries: An Imperative for Legal Research and the Administration of Justice in Nigeria*, emphasized the importance of resource sharing in libraries. They concluded that the ultimate goal of resource sharing is enabling a user in one library to access and retrieve the collections of several other libraries electronically, including downloading or printing full texts.

Mark and Gasen (2013) identified key reasons for libraries engaging in resource-sharing activities in the digital environment. These include broadening access to resources, lowering the per-unit cost of cataloguing and information delivery, fostering cooperation among member libraries, and addressing challenges such as copyright and governance through collaborative efforts.

Statement of the Problem

Resource sharing activities in libraries facilitate the seamless exchange of resources and services among institutions, with the primary goal of satisfying the diverse needs of library users. Resource sharing helps libraries overcome limitations in their collections and services, thereby ensuring equitable access to information for all users (Tanko, 2012). Academic libraries are expected to leverage partnerships and collaborative efforts to enhance the availability and quality of their offerings.

However, challenges have emerged in understanding the underlying motivations and factors driving resource-sharing activities. Existing literature, including studies by Obasola (2015), Adam and Usman (2013), Heloisa (2013), and Nwegbu, Echezona, and Obijido (2011),

highlights the importance of resource sharing but offers limited empirical evidence on the specific reasons academic libraries engage in such activities. This lack of clarity on the driving factors creates gaps in effectively planning and implementing resource-sharing initiatives.

This gap in understanding has affected academic libraries, particularly federal university libraries in Nigeria, by hindering their ability to fully optimize resource-sharing activities and maximize the benefits for library users. Without clear insights into the motivations and challenges, libraries risk ineffective collaborations and underutilization of shared resources.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the specific reasons that necessitate federal university libraries in Nigeria to engage in resource-sharing activities.

Research Objectives

The following objectives guided the study include:

1. To determine resource sharing activities among federal university libraries in Nigeria
2. To find out the agreement on the reasons for resource sharing activities among university libraries

Literature review

Resource sharing activities involve the exchange, provision, and sharing of resources and services among libraries to benefit library users. These activities encompass partnerships, interlibrary loans, cooperative cataloguing, cooperative reference services, cooperative acquisitions, personnel exchange, shared management information systems, and cooperative storage, among others, based on established agreements. Resource sharing represents a mode of operation where two or more libraries collaborate by exchanging resources and services for mutual benefit. The primary goal of these activities is to meet the diverse and growing needs of library users, providing a practical solution for libraries to overcome their limitations in resource and service provision (Nwegbu, Echezona, and Obijido, 2011).

Academic libraries worldwide are undergoing significant transformations in how they deliver services. Key factors driving these changes include the proliferation of information and communication technologies, the explosion of available information, increasing competition for limited funds, and rising user demands and expectations. These challenges underscore the urgency of resource-sharing activities, partnerships, and interlibrary collaboration as viable strategies to address these evolving demands (Johnson, 2012).

Arora and Trivedi (2010) highlighted that "no library can effectively satisfy its users with resources confined within its walls." In an era where the value of a library is increasingly measured by its ability to help users access universal information rather than the size of its

physical collection, resource sharing becomes indispensable. They emphasized that a country's economic progress and strength are often tied to the level of utilization of information resources. Consequently, libraries aim to pool resources to provide more satisfactory services to their users by increasing the availability of information resources and services.

The primary objective of resource sharing is to foster collaboration and share resources among participating libraries based on the principle of cooperation. In this context, the term 'resources' encompasses three key entities: personnel, materials, and financial resources. Through resource-sharing activities, libraries optimize their budgets while providing users with greater access to resources and services. This collaborative approach ensures the effective utilization of resources, enhancing service delivery and expanding access to information.

Resource sharing, cooperation, networks, and consortia are terms often used interchangeably to describe collaborative activities among libraries (Archana, 2014). The primary aim of these efforts is to provide expanded access to resources and services for user communities while adhering to copyright regulations. Additional objectives of library consortia include supporting resource-sharing activities through cooperative acquisition, enhancing Interlibrary Loan (ILL) and Document Delivery Services (DDS), rationalizing the use of funds among members, reducing subscription costs while maximizing resource utilization, and improving the skills of librarians to ensure effective resource and service provision.

Yernagula and Kelkar (2013) highlighted the benefits of consortia in their discussion of the Electronic Library Project (ELP) in Northern Ireland. These benefits include cost reduction, improved library service performance, broader public access to information, business transformation, equal participation of citizens in developing technological skills, and achieving better value for investments. Library systems, strengthened through consortia, enable librarians to meet user needs more effectively, as the advantages of collaboration become increasingly evident.

Oliveira and Cianconi (2013) emphasized the significance of consortia activities, particularly in developing countries like India, where public libraries face stiff competition from private academic institutions and decreased funding for higher education. This reduction in funding has driven the formation of library consortia to assist struggling libraries in managing their financial constraints. Such collaborations have become a strategic necessity, enabling libraries to pool resources, optimize budgets, and improve service delivery.

Johnson (2012) further observed that resource-sharing activities are vital and inevitable for libraries in developing countries, where shortages of funds and resources are common. Additionally, libraries face spatial challenges for storing resources, necessitating the adoption of networks and collaborative approaches.

Resource sharing has evolved significantly from its traditional concept of interlibrary lending. Today, it encompasses cooperative acquisition, collection development, shared cataloguing, centralized processing, the exchange of journal contents pages, bibliographic data sharing, centralized periodical collections, the exchange of electronic documents and articles, and obtaining photocopies of materials. Over the past two decades, advancements in Information Technology (IT) have played a pivotal role in expanding and modernizing resource-sharing practices, particularly in countries like India. These advancements have enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of resource-sharing activities, ensuring libraries remain relevant in the digital age.

Anna and Puspitasari (2013) conducted a qualitative survey to explore resource sharing, services, and barriers among well-established university libraries in Pakistan. Using interviews, they aimed to assess the status of collection sharing, identify reasons for non-participation, and propose solutions. The study revealed that only 13% of libraries participated in interlibrary loans, while 87% lacked formal resource-sharing programs. Barriers were categorized as *technical and procedural* (e.g., lack of automated catalogues, union catalogues, and web OPAC) and *psychological and behavioural* (e.g., librarians' lack of authority and fear of material loss). Recommendations included prioritizing web OPAC development, utilizing electronic media for efficient and secure sharing, and forming protocols for partnerships at local and national levels.

Lawal, Bassey, and Ani (2008) surveyed resource-sharing practices among law libraries in Nigerian universities. Respondents recognized the value of such practices, with most engaging in admittance and donation as common forms of sharing, while personnel exchange and cooperative classification were less common. However, the study highlighted the absence of written policies for resource sharing, insufficient copies of resources, and funding issues as key obstacles. Raising awareness and adopting formal sharing mechanisms were suggested as solutions.

Singh (2010) argued that no library could fully satisfy user needs with only its internal resources. He emphasized that a library's value is increasingly determined by its ability to connect users with global information. This perspective highlights the critical role of resource-sharing activities in enhancing access to universal knowledge.

Mark and Geason (2011) described library cooperation as a universal concept shaped by global economic and societal changes. They noted that partnerships, collaborations, and consortia enhance libraries' ability to adapt to modern challenges. Success stories in Africa illustrate how collaboration and networking have been used to lobby policymakers, share subscriptions for e-resources, build capacity, and improve services. Such efforts demonstrate the need for libraries

to overcome isolation, exchange knowledge, and adopt innovative practices to remain effective.

Varaprasad and Madhusudhan (2010) identified several benefits of resource-sharing networks, including improved resource utilization, mutual supplementation of institutional collections, faster information retrieval, global data flow, and enhanced professional development. However, financial constraints and rising costs of materials necessitate cooperative ventures to ensure access to sufficient resources.

John-Okeke (2013) highlighted additional drivers for resource-sharing activities, such as high costs of materials, increasing user demand for diverse formats, advances in ICT, and institutional pressure. These factors underscore the importance of collaboration in addressing resource gaps, optimizing library services, and meeting user needs.

Bourlakis and Bourlakis (2013) described resource sharing as an economical tool for enhancing library collections and services. Libraries can leverage both manual and electronic formats to facilitate sharing activities under mutual agreements. Anita (2015) similarly noted that no library can independently meet all user demands, advocating for extensive collaboration as the most viable solution. Tumbleson and Burke (2010) further emphasized that rising publication costs and shrinking budgets necessitate optimization through resource sharing.

Radnor and Shrauger (2012) outlined reasons for libraries to engage in resource sharing, including promoting accessibility, maximizing resource utilization, avoiding duplication, and ensuring faster delivery of services. Such efforts are vital in creating reciprocal exchanges and enhancing library value.

The review consistently underscores the necessity of resource sharing as no single library can independently meet all user needs. Resource sharing enables libraries to expand access, reduce costs, and optimize service delivery, particularly in developing regions. However, the studies reviewed largely focus on general or regional contexts and fail to specifically address resource-sharing practices in Nigerian federal university libraries. This gap forms the basis for the present study, which aims to examine the motivations and practices of resource sharing within these institutions.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design, which is suitable for collecting data at a specific point in time to examine the current state of resource-sharing practices among academic libraries in federal universities in Nigeria. The design enables the systematic

collection and analysis of data from a diverse and representative sample to address the research objectives effectively.

The study population comprised library staff in the academic libraries of 40 federal universities in Nigeria. Given the complexity and diversity of the population, a stratified random sampling technique was employed. The universities were stratified based on Nigeria's six geopolitical zones to ensure equitable representation. From each stratum, 50% of the federal universities were randomly selected, yielding a sample of 20 federal universities. These universities collectively employ 580 library staff, who formed the target population for this study.

A structured questionnaire was used as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was designed to capture relevant information on library staff's knowledge, practices, and perceptions of resource sharing. It consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions to facilitate comprehensive data collection. The instrument was validated through expert review and pilot-tested to ensure clarity, reliability, and relevance to the study objectives.

The questionnaires were administered physically and electronically (where applicable) to the 580 library staff across the 20 sampled universities. Adequate follow-up was conducted to maximize the response rate. Out of the 580 distributed questionnaires, 433 were completed and deemed valid for analysis, representing a 74.7% response rate. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores, were used to summarize and describe the demographic characteristics of respondents and key trends in resource-sharing practices.

Results:

Table 1. Reasons why university libraries must engage in Resource Sharing Activities

S/N	Statement on reasons	Yes, Freq(%)	No, Freq(%)
1	Promoting free flow of resources and services among libraries	433(100%)	0(0%)
2	Promoting mutual understanding among member libraries	433(100%)	0(0%)
3	Helping and avoid duplication of purchase among libraries	422(97.5%)	11(2.5%)
4	Helping in reducing the cost of library operations	419(96.8%)	14(3.2%)
5	Helping the user to leverages resources and services through virtual union catalogue among the libraries.	283(65.4%)	153(34.6%)
6	Increasing in demand for resources and services by users	404(93.3%)	29(6.7%)
7	Providing support for users to access different resources and services that are not available in the local library	422(97.5%)	11(2.5%)
8	Creating varieties of opportunities to share/exchange resources and services among member libraries	415(95.8%)	18(4.2%)
9	Helping in exchanging ideas, new technique, resources, services and experiences among the academic librarians	433(100%)	0(0%)

Table 1 indicates that all 433 respondents (100%) cited the following reasons for engaging in resource-sharing activities: promoting the free flow of resources among members, fostering mutual understanding among participating libraries, and facilitating the exchange of ideas, new techniques, resources, services, and experiences. These reasons were followed by 422 respondents (97.5%) who identified avoiding the duplication of purchases and providing greater support for users to access diverse resources and services unavailable in the local library.

In addition, 419 respondents (96.8%) highlighted reducing the cost of library operations and services, while 415 respondents (95.8%) emphasized creating various opportunities for sharing resources and services among libraries. Finally, more than half of the respondents, 283 (65.4%), indicated that helping users leverage resources and services through a virtual union catalog was among the key reasons for engaging in these activities.

Table 2. Agreement on the Reasons for Resource Sharing Activities in Libraries

S/N	Statements	A	UD	D	\bar{X}	SD
1	Promoting free flow of resources and services	320(73.9)	20(4.6)	93(21.5)	4.04	0.81
2	Promoting understanding among library members	287(66.3)	6(1.4)	140(32.3)	4.20	0.84
3	Helping to avoid duplication in purchasing of resources and services among members	312(72.1)	11(2.5)	110(25.4)	4.48	0.90
4	Helps in reducing the cost of library operations	306(70.7)	16(3.7)	111(25.6)	4.31	0.86
5	Helps the users to leverage resources and services through virtual union catalogue	328(75.8)	7(1.6)	98(22.6)	4.06	0.81
6	Increasing in demand for resources by the users	289(66.7)	2(5.1)	122(28.2)	4.16	0.83
7	Providing greater support for users to access different resources and services that are not available in their local libraries	273(63)	7(2)	103(35)	4.38	0.88
8	Creating opportunities to exchange resources and services among member libraries	323(74.6)	9(2.1)	101(23.3)	4.19	0.84
9	Helps in exchange of ideas, technique, resources, services and experiences among the librarians.	347(80.1)	15(3.5)	71(16.4)	4.08	0.87

Table 2 presents the respondents' agreement with the reasons why libraries under study engage in resource-sharing activities. A majority, 347 (80.1%), 328 (75.8%), 323 (74.6%), 320 (73.9%), and 306 (70.7%), agreed with the following statements as reasons for engaging in resource-sharing activities: promoting the free flow of resources and services among members, fostering mutual understanding, avoiding duplication in purchasing resources and services among members, reducing the cost of library operations and services, and helping users leverage resources and services through virtual union catalogs.

This was followed by more than half of the respondents, 289 (66.7%), 287 (66.3%), and 273 (63.3%), who provided additional reasons for engaging in resource-sharing activities, such as providing greater support for library users to access diverse resources and services, and creating various opportunities to share and exchange resources and services among members. By implication, the data indicate that the majority of respondents have multiple reasons for

participating in resource-sharing activities, with providing better access to a greater variety of resources and services being a key motivation.

Summary of the Findings

1. Most respondents cited promoting free resource flow, mutual understanding, cost reduction, and leveraging virtual union catalogues as key reasons for engaging in resource sharing
2. The majority agreed that resource sharing improves resource access, reduces duplication and costs, and enhances opportunities for collaboration.

Conclusion

Resource sharing activities are crucial for libraries aiming to meet the growing demands of their users for access to diverse resources and services, essential for teaching, learning, and research. The qualifications, work experience, and computer literacy of library staff play a significant role in the effective implementation of these activities. As the driving force behind daily library operations, library staff are pivotal in facilitating resource sharing, ensuring that libraries can adapt to the evolving needs of their users and continue to provide valuable services.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the research:

1. Libraries should invest in continuous professional development programmes for their staff, focusing on qualifications, work experience, and computer literacy, to improve the effectiveness of resource sharing activities.
2. Libraries should foster stronger collaborations and networking among institutions at local, national, and international levels to improve resource sharing.

Reference

- Adam, I. A. & Usman, I. (2013) Information Resources Sharing in Academic Libraries Services in Bauchi: The case study of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi and Muhammad Wabi Libraries Federal Polytechnic Bauchi. *Merit Research Journal of Education and Review*, 1(1), 1-5. Available online <http://www.meritresearchjournals.org/er/index.htm> accessed 20th March 2019.
- Ali, H., Owoeye, J. E. & Anasi, N.I. S. (2010). Resources Sharing among Law Libraries: An Imperative for Legal Research and the Administration of Justice in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 1-9. Retrieved on December 02, 2015, <http://www.digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/404/>.
- Anita, M. (2015). Resources sharing Activities of FIMT Campus Library. *Quest Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*. 3(3), available at www.questjournals.org.com accessed 22nd May, 2018
- Anna, N. E. V. & Puspitasari, D. (2013). Knowledge Sharing in Libraries: A Case Study of Knowledge Sharing Strategies. Indonesian University Libraries (Online). Available www.library.ifla.org/200/1/207-annaen.pdf. (October 20, 2018)
- Archana, S.N (2014). Resource sharing Among Engineering College Libraries Affiliated to Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala: A Proposed Model. Unpublished (PhD Thesis), Faculty of Technology Cochin University of Science and Technology.
- Arora, J., & Trivedi, K. (2010). UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium: present services and future endeavours. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 30(2), 15-25
- Bourlakis, C. & Bourlakis, M. (2013). Information Technology Safeguard, Logistics asset Specificity and Fourth Party Logistic Network Creation in the Food Retail Chain; *Journal of Business and International Marketing* 20(2). PAGES
- Heloisa, H. A. (2013). Sharing of Information and Cooperation among University Libraries and their Importance in the Networked World. *Library philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from: <http://www.digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/404/>.
- John-Okeke, R (2013). Bibliographic Networking and the Law Libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Sciences*, 5(1) 8-13.
- Johnson, I. M. (2012). Smart Cities, Smart Libraries and Smart Librarians in Shanghai Library(Ed) Smart Cities and Library Services. The Proceeding of the Sixth Shanghai International Library Forum. Shanghai Scientific and Technological Literature

Publishing House. Available at
<http://virtualikumpus oulu.fi/English/smartlibraryhtml> .

- Lawal, O. O; Bassey, B. A & Ani, O. E (2008). Resources Sharing among Nigerian University law libraries: A state of the art. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*. 3(2) 1-16. Retrieved December 04, 2015 from: <http://www.highbean.com../IGI-180748249.html/>
- Mark, T. & Gasen, K. (2013). *Community Partnerships: A Sustainable Resource for Non-Governmental Organizations*. St. Louis, MO: UMSL Public Policy Research, Library and Information Centre. Available at <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/Insight/ViewContentServlet?Filename=Publishe>. Accessed on 26th March, 2018.
- Mohammed, M. & Islam, R. (2013). Present Status of Library Co-operation, Networking and Resources Sharing in Bangladesh: Web-based Library Co-operation for Access to World-wide. *Information Library Philosophy and Practice*. 2(3), 1-17, available at <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/881> accessed on 19th September, 2016.
- Nwegbu, M. I. & Obijiofo, V. (2011). Promoting Resources sharing Between State and Federal University Libraries in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Library, Information and Archival Studies*, 1(2), 030-037. From <http://www.interestjournals.org/IRJLIAS>.
- Obasola, O. I. (2015). Building Capacity for Librarians for Knowledge and Skills Development. Retrieved on 4th June 2015 from: Collaborative librarianship.org/index.php/jocl/article/viewfile/319/253.
- Oliveira, C. B. & Cianconi, R. B. (2013). Co-operation, Sharing and Collaboration: The Case of the Network of Libraries on art in the State of Rio de Janeiro-Redarte/RJ. *Brazilian Journal of Information Science (BJIS)*, 2(1). PAGES
- Radnor, M. C. & Shrauger, K. J. (2012). Ebook Resources Sharing Models: Borrow, Buy, or Rent. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 22(3-4), 155-161. Accessed from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1072303X.2012.728186>
- Tanko, I. (2012). The Jos Carnegie Spirit Lives On. In: Liverpool, L.S.O (Ed.) Transformation through Partnership: The Carnegie Story. *Forthcoming*, pp. 86-91.

- Tumbleson, B.E. & Burke, J. J. (2010). When Life Hands You Lemons: Overcome Obstacles to Expand Services in an Embedded Librarian Program. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(6), 972-988
- Varaprasad, S. J. D. & Madhusudhan, S. (2010). E-Journal Consortium: Is it a Success Story always? *DESIDOC J. Library Information Technology*, 30(2), 92-96. www.Google.muhs.ac.inclsive.
- Yernagula, R & Kelkar, P. K. (2013). Library Consortia: Benefits and M Nodels. *Electronic Journal Consortia Library*. Available at <http://ecommons.luc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1006&context=libfacpub>.